

Speculations on a Union Between Media Literacy and Data Literacy

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Abstract

This thought piece suggests that varied technological convergences between different forms of media, information and communication technologies have led to potential, real, or perceived convergences among literacies, in particular in a union between media literacy and data literacy. This development should be taken into account, when planning and providing media literacy education.

Keywords: data literacy, media literacy, information literacy, convergences

Introduction

In their foundational paper, Livingstone, et al. state the following:

As broadcast, audiovisual and print media converge with telecommunications, computing, and information systems, could hardly remain separate. Indeed, despite their contrasting disciplinary backgrounds, theories, and methods, these research traditions have an increasingly similar object of inquiry: the public's understanding of and effective engagement with media, information and communication technologies of all kinds. We advocate a converged or at least dialogical concept of media and information "literacies", arguing that each tradition has much to learn from the other, although we accept that some differences must remain. (2008, p. 2)

Today, this idea should neither be restricted to research, nor to media literacy and information literacy. It must be seen rather as widely generalizable, comprehensive and valid for most "new literacies" even among the circumstances of continual technological change,

because converging technologies have triggered both the convergence of literacies, and the appearance of a number of literacies, not known before. This diversity is a welcome development, at least because it promises to bring in a consolidated set of approaches to varied literacy issues. On the other hand, we can speculate that the concept of data literacy emerged not only because of the convergence of different literacies, but because these convergences revealed literacies' potential to be broaden their circle to newer media.

The way towards critical literacies

An important step in acknowledging the above developments was the appearance of a 2018 definition of information literacy, which relates to information “in all its forms: not just print, but also digital content, data, images and the spoken word.” This definition also points out that there is an overlap between information literacy, media literacy, and data literacy (CILIP, 2018). This view is in accordance with the definition of digital literacy as “the ability to understand and use information in multiple formats from a wide variety of sources when it is presented via computers (Gilster, 1997).”

It has to be added here that a broad conceptualization of media literacy is not necessarily media specific, because such conceptualizations define primary skills, necessary for social development (e.g., critical thinking, social, or moral skills), which can be then adapted to specific media developments (Pfaff-Rüdiger and Riesmeyer, 2016., p. 169).

As early as in 2011, the importance of critical approaches was emphasised by advocating not only access to media, but understanding and producing media, and negotiating meanings, as well as caring for the quality and accuracy of content (Koltay, 2011). Nonetheless, Carmi et al (2020) indicate that the meaning of being critical is not always clear, but it should clearly include digital skills, aimed at developing the critical awareness of citizens by focusing on the role of communities, institutions, or technology companies.

With the aim of providing help for managing post-truth phenomena, science-related misinformation, and enabling more informed individual and collective decision-making, Howell and Brossard (2021) argue for science literacy, the definition of which should encompass knowledge and skills relevant across the information lifecycle of science, including issues, such as the COVID-19 pandemic and climate change.

They conceptualize three constituents of it:

- Civic science literacy includes the understanding not only of the processes and basic vocabulary of science, but also its impact on individuals and society;
- Digital media science literacy describes how this type of

information travels through media systems, can be accessed, and evaluated;

- Cognitive science literacy equals to the awareness of people's own biases in evaluating science information and media.

In 2013, data literacy was defined as transforming data into actionable knowledge, among others by interpreting, critically assessing, and using data (Calzada Prado, & Marzal, 2013). However, according to Pangrazio and Selwyn (2019, p. 215) in response to datafication, we should adopt literacies by making use of personal data, generated by our own digital practices. This leads to the appearance of personal data literacies that focus on data identification, understanding, reflexivity, uses, and tactics.

In our opinion, making use of personal data unavoidably requires applying the rather traditional techniques of personal information management (PIM), defined as an activity, in which an individual stores personal information items in order to retrieve them later (Bergman, 2013). Obviously, most of the abovementioned literacies may be applied for mitigating the symptoms of information overload (IO) (Koltay, 2017). Furthermore, PIM can prove useful when trying to mitigate the symptoms not only of IO but data overload, as well.

As mentioned above, there are efforts to elaborate the theory of critical data literacy by pointing out that data may reflect reductive views of the world, therefore the treatment of data should start from deconstructing its undisputed authority. This fact dictates that data literate persons should verify how data came to be, who and in what contexts created it. Closely related to these issues is that data is not neutral, therefore it should be considered as ideological (Špiranec et al., 2019).

Relying on critical media literacy, Sander (2020, p. 5) directs attention to the potential of critical big data literacy. She argues that its aim is to enable people to “question and scrutinise the socio-technical systems of big data practices, to weigh the evidence, to build informed opinions on current debates around data analytics as well as to allow them to make informed decisions on personal choices such as which data to share or which services to use.”

As Carmi et al. (2020, p. 13) argue, moving in this direction requires models of data literacy that focus on literacies beyond the individual. They also suggest that “understanding the digital economy, including how algorithms work and who is funding social media platforms is a key issue in regard to data literacies.” They also point out the need for including data thinking in the sense of citizens' critical understanding of data. To this comes data doing, understood as citizens' everyday engagements with data, including using data in an ethical way. Data participation means proactive engagement with data and their networks, among others by helping fellow citizens with

their data literacy (Yates et al. 2020). These ideas must drive educational programmes that are run on an “ongoing basis to tackle new emerging media changes and make sure people from various background have appropriate access and resources to gain such literacies”. These efforts should suit people’s everyday needs (Carmi et al., 2020).

An integral part of the teaching-learning process relates to (re)politicizing abstract issues into the social, political, and economic context of datafication. This will lead to “empowerment, notions about the abilities and needs of the learners and the neutrality of the practice, which run the risk of discounting the power structures that enable and perpetuate systemic inequalities” (Jansen, 2021, p. 10).

Convergences & similarities in the pedagogy of literacies

Not all conceptualisations of data literacy are easily applied to teaching and learning, among others because in formal learning environments it is difficult to translate them from formal data contexts to personal ones (Bowler et al. (2017).

The idea of data infrastructure literacy is one of the starting points to argue for allowing the learner “to account for, intervene around, and participate in the wider socio-technical infrastructures through which data is created, stored and analysed” (Gray et al., 2018, p. 8).

While there should be education about the broader implications of datafication, it is challenging to translate abstract learning objectives into practical models. One of the reasons is that “the material ‘form’ of data significantly influences how meaning can be made from the information it represents. In its unprocessed and un-coded state, data might be collected in greater volume and appear more ‘objective’ than selectively curated data sets: however, it is largely indecipherable and can require complicated technology and specialised expertise” (Pangrazio, & Sefton Green, 2020, p. 212). Nonetheless, the principles of data literacy, put forward by Wolff et al. (2019, p. 49) include guided inquiry that encourages students to “focus on how a small part of the data set represents phenomena”. This also means that it is advisable to focus on local contexts of data, i.e. encouraging teachers to use data that is local to students, as well as developing data skills as it may encourages students to analyse data they have collected themselves. As Abner (2020, p. 20) puts it, a data literate person “will ask questions about how the value is determined, who assigns the value, and what societal factors might influence the value.” Answers to these questions are not always readily (if at all) available. However, “when learners understand the process of data creation as wholly guided by humans, they think critically about that process and how that affects any data they examine”. Perhaps the most recent example of this is media literacy in the age of machine learning that renews the requirement for making use of computational thinking. As Valtonen et al. (2019, p. 28) argue, “in

order to gain the abilities for critical thinking and media literacy in the age of media automation, media literacy education and computational thinking have to be tightly intertwined in education.” Drawing mainly on concepts of computer science, computational thinking helps understanding human behaviour that involves a way of solving problems by requiring thinking at multiple levels of abstraction and focusing on thought processes that can be operationalized (Wing, 2006). It also includes skills of algorithmic thinking, navigating multiple levels of abstraction and data modelling taught with or without the use of computers (Jacob, & Warschauer, 2018). Despite its importance, data-literate and media-literate persons must be also aware of the limitations of computational thinking, among others because they should understand the limitations of data and remain able to act in the absence of data. To follow this direction successfully, educational institutions at the primary, secondary, and post-secondary levels need make use of experiential learning that gives prominence that relies on the ability to collaborate, work in groups, read social cues, and respond adaptively (Davies, Fidler, & Gorbis, 2011, p. 13).

Conclusion

Convergences probably never end as old convergences can be followed by new ones. On the other hand, literacies, mentioned in this paper are growingly branching out into derived (sub)literacies. This is especially true for critical approaches that emphasize targeting less prescriptive and measurable types of literacy (Špiranec et al., 2016), as well as social practice that is enacted in social settings (Lloyd, & Hicks, 2021).

Health literacy has the potential “to empower people to make informed health decisions and to practice healthy and protective behaviours” (Okan et al. (2020, p. 1). Moreover, critical health literacy is also tied to conflict situations, when “interventions are complicated or inconsistent and when fundamental values of self-interest versus communal solidarity clash” (Abel, & McQueen, 2020, p. 1613). Media literacy can become not only critical, but post-digital, as it is expected to be attentive to issues beyond the social mediation of questionable information by investigating the ways, in which “bots and other algorithms are deployed and taken up by disparate and conflicting social actors” (Jiang, & Vetter, 2020, p. 87). In parallel with these developments, there is also a need for changing the approaches to teaching different literacies by taking into account varied literacies. For instance, when Sander (2020, p. 12) underlines, how valuable it is “presenting real-life examples of data harm that demonstrate how even ‘harmless’ data can be used for questionable causes and could potentially have negative consequences”, she adds that this is true for any media content. Similarly, the idea of data infrastructure literacy, proposed by Gray et al. (2018) is one of the starting points to argue for allowing the learner “to account for, intervene around, and participate in the wider socio-technical infrastructures through which

data is created, stored and analysed” (p. 8). This function is undisputedly relevant for the whole range of literacies, including media literacy.

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